

TREAT-AD

TaRget Enablement to Accelerate
Therapy Development for AD

IUSM-Purdue TREAT-AD Center Target Enabling Component

PTPN6/SHP1 biochemical assays

NCBI Gene ID / UniProt ID / EC	5777/P2935
Authors	Zihan QU, Jiajun Dong, and Zhong-Yin Zhang
Collaborating Authors	
Date Approved by Admin Core	September 21 st , 2023
Document version	V1
Document version date	September 20 th , 2023
Citation	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8367741
Affiliations	Departments of Medicinal Chemistry and Molecular Pharmacology, and of Chemistry, Institute for Drug Discovery, Purdue University

Protein expression constructs and SHP1 protein purification

SHP1 PTP domain (245-543) and full-length constructs (1-597) were cloned into pET28a(+) vector via molecular cloning. Both constructs were sequenced, and no mutations were observed, suggesting the cloning was successful. Each construct was overexpressed in *E. coli* of BL21(DE3) strain and purified by Ni-NTA column and size exclusion column (SEC). PTP domain and full-length constructs were obtained of high yield (30 mg per liter of culture) and high purity (>95% pure by SDS gel).

Figure 1. SDS gel of SHP1 PTP domain (~34 kDa) and full length (~68 kDa).

Kinetic characterization of SHP1 proteins

The enzymatic kinetics of full-length SHP1 has not been well characterized and there are conflicting data on whether full-length SHP1 adopts an autoinhibited conformation under physiological conditions. A thorough characterization of both PTP domain and full-length constructs will allow a better understanding of the regulatory mechanism of the enzyme and guide the development of allosteric assays.

The enzymatic kinetics of PTP domain and full-length constructs were determined using para-nitrophenyl phosphate (pNPP) and 6,8-difluoro-4-methylumbelliferyl phosphate (DiFMUP) as substrates. SHP1 full-length showed a $K_m > 200$ mM against pNPP, preventing acquisition of K_{cat} and K_m values, but it has a lower K_m towards DiFMUP which enabled a thorough characterization. SHP1 PTP domain which lacks both SH2 domains and the last 54 residues exhibited enhanced phosphatase activity than full-length. The lower phosphatase activity of SHP1 full-length suggested that it adopts an autoinhibited conformation under physiological condition. These results shed a light on the regulation mechanism in cells and animals and also serve as a guidance for allosteric assay development.

Figure 2. Kinetics parameters of (A): SHP1 PTP domain against pNPP. (B): SHP1 full-length against pNPP. (C): SHP1 PTP domain against DiFMUP. (D): SHP1 full-length against DiFMUP.

Biophysical assay development for target engagement evaluation.

Materials – Proteins and Fluorescent Dye. Recombinant SHP1 PTP domain and SHP1 FL were expressed and purified as described. The phosphatase activity of each enzyme was examined, and inactive enzymes were replaced with fresh preps using the same plasmids stocks in house. The assay was performed in Bis-Tris buffer (100 mM Bis-Tris, pH 6.5, 100 mM NaCl, 5% DMSO). The commercially available SPYRO orange was acquired from the Chemical Genomic Facility, aliquoted, and stored under -80 °C. The sodium orthovanadate was prepared in stock as previously described, aliquoted, and stored under -20 °C.

Assay Development for Differential Scanning Fluorimetry (DSF) Assay. The DSF assay depends on a fluorescence dye, SPYRO orange in this case, to monitor the unfold of proteins as temperature rises. The SPYRO dye is hydrophobic, so it will bind to exposed hydrophobic sites of proteins and emit fluorescence as protein gradually unfold. At certain temperature, the protein will aggregate together and dissociate with the fluorescent dye, at which stage the fluorescence intensity will drop back down. When the protein is bound with a small molecule, this unfold process will be affected, which is reflected by the change of melting temperature T_m .

Figure 3. Schematic illustration of the thermal shift process and the fluorescence intensity change as temperature increases.

Using the recombinant protein alone, we determined the optimal protein and dye concentrations for both constructs (10 μM protein and 15X SPYRO orange for PTP domain and 5 μM protein and 20X SPYRO orange for FL). The assay setup was validated by examining the effects of vanadate, a pan-PTP reversible inhibitor. As expected, the T_m vanadate (250 μM) treated SHP1 PTP domain increased by 1.29 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ compared with DMSO treated protein, suggesting that the assay is robust and can be used to evaluate target engagement of acquired hits. As no allosteric inhibitor has been reported for SHP1 FL and that the protein adopts an autoinhibited conformation, not control experiment was performed for SHP1 FL.

Figure 4. Vanadate increased the T_m of SHP1 PTP domain by 1.29 $^{\circ}\text{C}$, indicating the assay is robust.

Assay Development of Protein Thermal Shift Assay. As a cross validation assay, we also developed a protein thermal shift assay to corroborate with the DSF assay. The protein thermal shift assay also involves compound pretreatment (2 μM recombinant protein), after which the solution will be aliquoted (45 μL) to PCR tubes and heated up at different temperatures for 3.5 minutes. The solutions were centrifuged and the supernatant (30 μL) was loaded to SDS gel to quantify remaining proteins. To allowing an accurate quantification, recombinant CDC14A, a thermal stable phosphatase, was added as loading control for all experiments.

Assay development for SHP1 inhibitors targeting the active site.

Screening Materials – Proteins and Reporter Substrates. Recombinant SHP1 PTP domain was expressed and purified as described for the primary screening. Closely related phosphatase SHP2 and other phosphatases such as LYP and PTP1B were previously expressed and purified and will serve as the target for counter screening and generation of selectivity profile. The phosphatase activity of each enzyme was examined, and

inactive enzymes were replaced with fresh preps using the same plasmids stocks in house. The commercially available pNPP was purchased and made into stock solution using the assay buffer. The pH was calibrated with pH meter and the pH paper, and the stock was aliquoted and stored under -20 °C.

In vitro assay development for HTS. The assay was optimized from the in-house pNPP assay using identical enzyme and pNPP concentrations. An “excellent-range” Z score of 0.85 was determined for the optimized assay and known PTP inhibitor vanadate was tested to confirm the assay’s utility for screening and IC₅₀ determination.

High-throughput Screening. The pNPP assay was utilized to screen ~150 diverse phosphotyrosine mimic fragments to identify potential scaffolds for lead development. All compounds were screened at 50 µM against SHP1 PTP domain, which should bias the screen to identify active site (i.e. orthosteric) reversible inhibitors. Acquired hits were screened with 0.01% Triton X-100 to rule out aggregators followed by screening against SHP2 PTP domain to preliminarily examine the selectivity. 75 compounds showed >50% inhibition in the primary screening and showed comparable activity with 0.01% Triton X-100. The compounds were grouped into 8 series based on the core scaffold, and the dose-dependence of all compounds against SHP1 and SHP2 PTP domain were determined.

Binding and Mode of Action Characterization. To further understand the mode of action of each series, K_i was determined for the representative hits. Both benzothiazole and benzoxazole series showed a competitive mode of action which is consistent with the phosphotyrosine mimetics design. At the same time, the thermal shift assay has been optimized to determine the binding of hits to SHP1 PTP domain. This assay can be used to measure the melting temperature (T_m) of a protein. At the melting temperature, 50% of the protein will be denatured. The denaturation process can be monitored using a dye which binds to hydrophobic regions of the protein during the denaturation process causing an enhancement of the dye’s fluorescence intensity. When a compound binds a protein, a change in that protein’s T_m is often the result. To establish this assay for SHP1, the reaction conditions (protein concentration, type of dye, and dye concentration) were optimized to obtain a good melting curve. The SPYRO orange dye was found to work best with SHP-1 PTP domain at a protein concentration of 10 µM in a 20 µL reaction volume. The melting temperature of the SHP-1 PTP domain in 5% DMSO was found to be 37.7 ± 0.02 °C. This assay condition was validated with a known pan-PTP inhibitor, orthovanadate. At 250 µM, orthovanadate (5% DMSO) can change the T_m of SHIP1 to 39.3 ± 0.4 °C, a shift of 1.29 ± 0.05 °C. In the future, this compound can be used as our positive control when confirming the binding of the inhibitor to SHIP1 catalytic domain.

Assay development for covalent SHP1 inhibitors

Screening Materials – Proteins and Reporter Substrates. Both proteins and substrates were obtained and stored under identical condition as described in active site inhibitor HTS assay development part.

In vitro assay development for HTS. Unlike assays that characterize reversible inhibitors, covalent assays generally involve a preincubation part that allow irreversible modification of the protein by the compounds because covalent inhibitors are time dependent. The remaining enzymatic activity is usually characterized by diluting the mixture with substrate to minimize the impact of compounds. During optimization in 96-well plate, enzyme concentration, pNPP concentration, and enzymatic reaction time were optimized to generate maximal response with minimal compound interference, and the reaction time is ensured within the linear range. The setup was adapted to 384-well plate and optimized to a Z’ of 0.69. Known covalent inhibitor phenylvinylsulfonate (PVSN) was included in the assay to confirm the assay’s utility for screening.

Figure 5. Scheme of covalent assay setup.

Second, to characterize the kinetics parameters of acquired hits and lead derivatives, a colorimetric time-course assay was developed. After mixing the substrate, enzyme, and serial diluted compounds, the progress of enzymatic reaction was monitored using plate reader over the course of 60 min. The progress curve of each compound concentration will be fitted to the equation $Abs = v_0 \cdot (1 - \exp(-k_{obs} \cdot t)) / k_{obs}$, where v_0 is the initial rate of the enzyme, t is the time of reaction in second, and k_{obs} is the pseudo first-order rate constant. The obtained k_{obs} will be plotted against compound concentration. Such k_{obs} vs [inhibitor] plot will be fitted either to $Y = K_{inact} \cdot X / (k_i + X)$ to determine both K_{inact} and k_i or a linear line where the slope is directly K_{inact} / k_i . The assay was calibrated by testing PVSN against SHP2 PTP domain, the obtained K_{inact} / k_i is $189.2 \text{ M}^{-1} \text{ min}^{-1}$, which is comparable to previously tested $\sim 196.0 \text{ M}^{-1} \text{ min}^{-1}$. The result suggested that the assay is robust and reproducible to accurately characterize kinetics parameters of covalent inhibitors.

Baseline-corrected of PVSN: SHP1CD Inactivation: Abs vs. Time

Fit progress curves to $A = v_0(1 - e^{-k_i t}) / k_i$ to calculate k (k_{obs}) for each concentration of inhibitor.

PVSN: k_{obs} vs. [I]

Figure 6. Determination of kinetics parameters of PVSN against SHP2 using the time-course assay.

Thirdly, to determine the selectivity of acquired compounds, the IC_{50} assay for covalent inhibitor was optimized based on previous in-house protocol. The assay was initiated by the preincubation between enzyme and serial diluted compounds. After certain time, in this case, 10 min and 60 min, 4 μL of the mixture was transferred out followed by 50-fold dilution using pNPP above the K_m value to saturate the enzyme and wash off any unbound compounds. This enzymatic reaction would be quenched with 5-N NaOH followed by reading OD_{405} to determine IC_{50} . The assay setup allows a fair comparison between different target at a fixed time of preincubation and validation of time-dependence of acquired compound; additionally, the obtained values could serve as a reference for any cellular to animal studies.

Mode of Action and Intrinsic Reactivity Assay Development. Besides potency and selectivity, whether the acquired hits or derivatives target the cysteine in the active site pocket is important to rule out promiscuous or

highly reactive compounds. To determine whether a compound targets the active site cysteine, the compound will be incubated with the target enzyme in the presence or absence of orthovanadate. Because the orthovanadate is a competitive inhibitor of many PTPs, it will compete for the active site with the tested compound but will be washed off upon dilution because it is not a covalent inhibitor. Therefore, this competition will protect the active site from being inactivated and allows fully recovered enzymatic activity after dilution.

Figure 7. Vanadate protection assay setup.

The intrinsic reactivity assay was set up using reduced glutathione (GSH) as the substrate because it is a ubiquitously expressed antioxidant in cells and could accurately reflect the intrinsic reactivity of a compound in cells or animals. Unlike previously reported LC-MS method (Resnick et al. J. Am. Chem. Soc., 2019) that quantifies remaining compounds and of lower throughput, the optimized assay quantifies remaining GSH by 5,5'-dithiobis-(2-nitrobenzoic acid) (DTNB). Specifically, the compound and GSH were mixed in a 1:1 ratio in the assay buffer for 45 min, and the reaction was quenched by the addition of DTNB that reacts quickly with the thiolate on GSH and produces a yellow color with absorbance at 412 nm. The relative intrinsic reactivity can be efficiently determined in a higher throughput by comparing with known PTP covalent inhibitor and DMSO.

Figure 8. Scheme of DTNB quantification of GSH.

Assay development for biochemical HTS screening of SHP1 allosteric inhibitors

Assay development for HTS. The allosteric assay was optimized based on reported SHP2 allosteric assay (Chen et al. 2016). A 10-residue peptide from CD33 receptor (CD33_pY340), one of the SHP1 upstream, was utilized as the activating peptide to shift SHP1 from closed autoinhibited conformation to open active conformation. This allowed maximized signal-to-noise ratio and identification of small molecules that stabilize the autoinhibited conformation. The EC_{50} and maximal fold activation of CD33_pY340 was determined to be 1.6 μ M and 16-fold, respectively. The assay was optimized in both 96-well and 384-well plates for HTS and further *in vitro* characterization. An “excellent-range” Z score of 0.75 was determined for the optimized assay, was tested to confirm the assay’s utility for screening and IC_{50} determination.